

Hormone Receptor Status in Breast Carcinoma: A Study on Prognostic and Demographic Factors in an Indian Healthcare SettingKalpesh Chaudhari¹, Fuzeil Dhebar², Kailash Jawade³, Anil Gvalani⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, School of Medicine, D.Y. Patil Deemed-To-Be University, Nerul, Navi Mumbai-400706²Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, AIIMS Raipur³Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, School of Medicine, D.Y. Patil Deemed-To-Be University, Nerul, Navi Mumbai-400706⁴Professor, Department of General Surgery, School of Medicine, D.Y. Patil Deemed-To-Be University, Nerul, Navi Mumbai-400706

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Abstract:

Breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer among women globally and is projected to surpass lung cancer as the leading type by 2025. In India, rising incidences necessitate effective screening and standardized protocols, particularly in resource-limited settings. This observational study aimed to assess the incidence of hormone receptor status in breast carcinoma and its correlation with demographic and prognostic factors. Conducted at Dr. D.Y. Patil Hospital, Navi Mumbai, the study included 30 female patients who underwent Modified Radical Mastectomy (MRM). Hormone receptor statuses (ER, PR, HER2) were analyzed along with clinicopathological data. Results showed that the majority of patients (40%) were aged 41 to 60, and invasive ductal carcinoma was the predominant histological type (93.33%). Lymph node involvement was observed in 73.33% of patients, and tumour size between 2-5 cm was present in 70%. ER positivity was noted in 46.67% of patients, while PR positivity was observed in 50%, and HER2 positivity was seen in 43.33%. Correlations between age and hormone receptor status indicated significant associations, particularly for ER and PR. ER-positive tumours were more likely to be larger (>5 cm) and in advanced stages (III and IV), while PR-positive patients exhibited similar correlations with tumour size and lymph node involvement.

Keywords: Breast cancer, Hormone receptor status, Estrogen receptor (ER), Progesterone receptor (PR), HER2, Modified Radical Mastectomy (MRM).

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Introduction

Breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer in women globally, expected to surpass lung cancer as the leading type by 2025. By 2030, cases are projected to exceed two million worldwide. In India, breast cancer incidence has risen sharply, with over 118,000 cases reported in 2016 alone. Effective screening hinges on standardized protocols, appropriate diagnostic tools, and skilled personnel to minimize unnecessary interventions and false positives.

Mammography, despite its limitations in dense breast tissue and resource-poor settings like India, remains a primary tool, with sensitivity ranging from 53% to 67% and specificity from 89% to 99%. Hormone receptor status (ER, PR, HER2) guides therapeutic decisions, impacting treatment efficacy and patient outcomes. Although breast self-examination is recommended as a Breast Cancer early detection approach, it can be a helpful

adjunct if performed persistently and skillfully to help the woman become aware of her normal breast [1] The utility of ER expression as a diagnostic biomarker for breast cancer is further facilitated by its observed association with family history of the disease, especially in cases of familial risk. In addition, ER-36 expression was analysed by Konan et al. It is also one of the prognostic indicators and possible targets of PR-positive malignancies. [1-3]. Patients with ER- and PR- expressing tumours perform better than those without. Numerous studies have shown that overexpression of HER2/neu impairs response to tamoxifen and reduces overall survival. These immunohistochemical receptors are routinely tested for prognostic purposes in the treatment of breast cancer patients. Successful protocols for early identification and screening are required for maintaining low mortality [4-7]

Objective:

Aim: Assessment of incidence of hormone receptor status in breast carcinoma and demography and prognostic factors

Primary Objective: To analyze the demographic factors in hormone receptor positive in carcinoma breast

Secondary Objective: To assess the incidence and to analyze the prognostic factors

Materials and Methods:

a. Study design: An Observational study

b. Study duration: 2021-2022

c. Study site: Dr. D. Y. Patil Hospital, Nerul, Navi Mumbai

d. Eligibility Criteria:**Inclusion Criteria**

- Patient Giving Consent
- All Operated Cases of Breast Carcinoma
- Female

Exclusion Criteria

- Age Less Than 25
- Patients Not Giving Consent

e. Sample Size: 30 Patients

f. Study procedure: Patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included in the study. A written informed consent was taken. The postoperative hormone receptor status was noted.

The patient was observed post-operatively till discharge to note the prognosis.

g. Ethical consideration: Approval of Institutional Ethics Committee was taken before start of the study.

h. Consent: A written signed informed consent (in English, Hindi or Marathi) was taken prior to enrolling the subject in the study.

i. Investigations: All 30 patients were diagnosed as a case of breast carcinoma on core cut biopsy

j. Operation: All 30 patients went MRM (Modified Radical Mastectomy)

k. Drain: Drain was kept in all 30 patients

l. Morbidity: Out of 30 patients, 20 patients had morbidity.

m. Axillary Nodes: Out of 30 patients, in 18 patients axillary nodes were detected clinically. On HPE 22 patients had positive nodal status.

n. Chemotherapy: Out of 30 patients, 13 underwent neo adjuvant chemotherapy.

22 patients underwent adjuvant chemotherapy.

Results:

In the present study, out of 30 patients, 40 percent of the patients belonged to the age group of 41 to 60 years while 33.33 percent of the patients belonged to the age group of more than 60 years. 26.67 percent of the patients belonged to the age group of 25 to 40 years. Mean age of the patients was 52.73 years.

In the present study, right side involvement was seen in 53.33 percent while left side involvement was seen in 46.67 percent of the breast cancer patients respectively. Similar findings were reported in the past literature.

In the present study, while assessing the patients with breast carcinoma, it was seen that 93.33 percent of the patients were of invasive ductal type while the remaining 6.67 percent of the patients were of invasive lobular type. .

In the present study, out of 30 patients, tumour size was between 2 to 5 cm in 70 percent of the patients while it was more than 5 cm in 23.33 percent of the patients. Tumour size was less than 2 cm in 6.67 percent of the patients. In the present study, out of 30 breast cancer patients, lymph node involvement occurred in 73.33 percent of the patients.

In the present study, out of 30 patients with breast cancer, ER Positive; PR Positive status was seen in 36.67 percent of the patients with ER Negative; PR Negative status was seen in 40 percent of the patients. ER Positive; PR Negative status and ER Negative; PR Positive status were seen in 10 percent and 13.33 percent of the patients respectively. Overall, ER Positivity was seen in 46.67 percent of the patients while PR positivity was seen in 50 percent of the patients.

In the present study, HER2 status was positive in 43.33 percent of the patients with breast cancer.

Age with ER Status among Breast Carcinoma Patients

In the present study, while assessing the correlation of age with ER status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained. Majority of the ER positive patients belonged to the age group of 41 to 60 years.

Age with PR Status among Breast Carcinoma Patients

While assessing the correlation of age with PR status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained. Majority of the PR positive patients belonged to the age group of 41 to 60 years.

HER2 status	Number of patients	Percentage
Positive	14	43.33
Negative	16	56.67
Total	30	100

Table and Graph 1: Distribution among patients according to HER2

Age with Her2 Status among Breast Carcinoma Patients

While assessing the correlation of age with HER2 status among breast carcinoma patients, non-significant results were obtained. Majority of the HER2 positive patients belonged to the age group of 41 to 60 years.

Prognostic Factors and ER Status among Breast Carcinoma Patients While assessing the correlation of tumour size with ER status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained.

Majority of the ER positive patients were of tumour size of more than 5 cm. While assessing the correlation of lymph node status with ER status, significant results were obtained. All the breast cancer patients with lymph node involvement were ER positive. While assessing the correlation of tumour stage with ER status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained. Majority of the ER positive patients belonged to the stage III and stage IV.

Age group (years)	ER Positive		ER Negative		Total	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
25 to 40	3	42.5	5	57.5	8	100
41 to 60	8	66.67	4	33.33	12	100
More than 60	3	30	7	70	10	100
Total	14	46.67	16	53.33	30	100
p- value	0.001 (Significant)					

Table and Graph 2: Correlation of age with ER status among breast carcinoma patients

Prognostic Factors and PR Status among Breast Carcinoma Patients

While assessing the correlation of tumour size with PR status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained. Majority of the PR positive patients had tumour size of more than 5 cm. While assessing the correlation of lymph node status with PR status, significant results were obtained. All the breast cancer patients with lymph node involvement were PR positive. While assessing the correlation of tumour stage with PR status among breast carcinoma patients, significant

results were obtained. Majority of the PR positive patients belonged to the stage III and stage IV. The steroid hormone receptors ER and PR are two critical molecules for assessing the heterogeneity of breast cancer and the benefit of therapy.

The clinical significance of the hormone receptor status, especially in single hormone receptor-positive breast cancers, has not been fully understood to date and has not been investigated adequately because of the limited sample sizes. ER and PR expressions are prognostic factors showing a good prognosis in breast cancers (Senel F)

ER/PR status	Number of patients	Percentage
ER Positive; PR Positive	11	36.67
ER Positive; PR Negative	3	10
ER Negative; PR Positive	4	13.33
ER Negative; PR Negative	12	40
Total	30	100

Table and Graph 3: Distribution of patient according to ER / PR status

Prognostic Factors and Her2 Status among Breast Carcinoma Patients

While assessing the correlation of tumour size with HER2 status among breast carcinoma patients, non-significant results were obtained. While assessing the correlation of lymph node status with HER2 status, non-significant results were obtained. While assessing the correlation of tumour stage with HER2 status among breast carcinoma patients, non-significant results were obtained.

HER2 amplified breast cancers have unique biological and clinical characteristics. They have increased sensitivity to certain cytotoxic agents such as doxorubin, relative resistance to hormone agents and propensity to metastasize to the brain and viscera. These tumors have higher proliferation rates

and are associated with poorer patient prognosis. The poor outcome is dramatically improved with appropriate chemotherapy combined with the HER2 targeting drug trastuzumab

Conclusion:

While assessing the correlation of tumour size with HER2 status among breast carcinoma patients, non-significant results were obtained. While assessing the correlation of lymph node status with HER2 status, non-significant results were obtained. While assessing the correlation of tumour stage with HER2 status among breast carcinoma patients, non-significant results were obtained. While assessing the correlation of tumour size with PR status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained. Majority of the PR positive patients

had tumour size of more than 5 cm. While assessing the correlation of lymph node status with PR status, significant results were obtained. All the breast cancer patients with lymph node involvement were PR positive. While assessing the correlation of tumour stage with PR status among breast carcinoma patients, significant results were obtained. Majority of the PR positive patients belonged to the stage III and stage IV.

Bibliography

1. Ahead. World J Clin Oncol. 2022 Mar 24; 13(3):209-218. Mittra I, Mishra GA, Dikshit RP, Gupta S, Kulkarni VY, Shaikh HKA, Shastri SS,
2. Lao X.Q., Wang X., et al. Familial Risks and Estrogen Receptor-Positive Breast Cancer in Hong Kong Chinese Women. PLoS ONE. 2015; 10:c0120741.
3. Konan H.-P., Kassem L., Omarjee S., Surmicliova-Ganès A., Jacquemetton J.
4. Cascales E. Rezza A., Trédan O., Treilleux I., Poulard C., et al. ERa-36 regulates progesterone receptor activity in breast cancer. Breast Cancer Res. 2020; 22:50.
5. ND HER-2/neu status in breast carcinoma. Asian Journal of Medical Sciences. 2022, 13(5): 108- 112. Chen XS, Ma CD, Wu JY, Yang WT, Lu HE, Wu J, et al. Molecular subtype
7. Approximated by quantitative estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor and Her2 can predict the prognosis of breast cancer. Tumori. 2010;96(1:103-110.
8. Ariga R, Zarif A, Korasick J, Reddy V, Sizio-pikouK and Gattuso P. Correlation of Her2/neu gene amplification with other prognostic and predictive factors in female breast carcinoma. Breast J. 2005; 11(4):278-280.
9. Huang HJ, Neven P, Drijkoningen M, Paridaens R, Wildiers H, Van Limbergen E, et al. Association between tumor characteristics and HER-2/neu by immuno-histochemistry in 1362 women with primary operable breast cancer. J Clin Pathol. 2005; 58(6):61 1-616.